

Contents lists available at [ScienceDirect](https://www.sciencedirect.com)

International Journal of Educational Research

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/ijedures

“Sometimes I just smile, even though I didn’t understand”: Perspectives of students with hearing loss on participation in mainstream schools

Lara Hardebeck^{a,*}, Esther Ruigendijk^b, Ulla Licandro^a ^a Department of Special Needs Education and Rehabilitation, Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg and Cluster of Excellence Hearing4all, Oldenburg, Germany^b Department of Dutch Studies and Cluster of Excellence Hearing4all, Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg, Oldenburg, Germany

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Hearing loss
Participation
Mainstream schools
Student perspective
Classroom strategies

ABSTRACT

Participation in school is crucial for students’ social development and academic success. Students with hearing loss face multiple participation challenges in mainstream schools, affecting personal, social, and educational dimensions. Mainstream classrooms rely heavily on verbal communication, making it challenging for them to follow lessons, interact with classmates, and access curricular content. However, few studies have directly explored students’ own perspectives on these challenges, leaving a gap in understanding the factors that promote or hinder meaningful school participation. This study explores the perspectives of students with hearing loss regarding their participation in mainstream schools, emphasizing both their lived experiences and their recommendations for improving participation. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with 26 German-speaking students aged 7 to 16 to investigate environmental and personal factors that shape school participation. Findings indicate that positive experiences were associated with supportive teacher and peer behaviours, effective classroom management, and the use of adaptive communication strategies. Conversely, key barriers included high levels of background noise, rapid speech, inconsistent implementation of assistive listening technologies, and limited awareness of hearing loss among teachers and classmates. Students described employing a variety of coping strategies—such as self-advocacy, behavioural adjustments, and tailored communication tactics—to navigate these challenges. However, they also reported challenges stemming from listening fatigue, social anxiety, and the emotional strain of feeling different. To improve participation, students proposed several practical strategies, including consistent and correct use of assistive technologies by teachers, structured classroom routines, increased use of visual supports, differentiated instruction, quieter group settings, and scheduled listening breaks. The findings underscore the importance of learner-centred approaches, promoting both academic and social participation. They also highlight the critical role of teachers, peers, and school-wide policies in creating inclusive environments that address the diverse needs of students with hearing loss.

* Corresponding author at: Department of Special Needs Education and Rehabilitation, Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg, Ammerländer Heerstraße 114-118, 26129 Oldenburg, Germany.

E-mail address: lara.hardebeck@uni-oldenburg.de (L. Hardebeck).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2025.102874>

Received 23 September 2025; Received in revised form 11 November 2025; Accepted 12 November 2025

Available online 19 November 2025

0883-0355/© 2025 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. Introduction

Involvement in school activities, including interactions with teachers and classmates, supports social development and overall well-being (Carlborg & Granlund, 2019; Maxwell et al., 2018). Participation, defined as “a person’s involvement in a life situation” (World Health Organization, 2001, p. 10), is a fundamental right. Beyond mere attendance, involvement reflects the subjective experience of participation (Imms et al., 2016, 2017). In schools, Maciver and colleagues (2019, p. 5) describe participation as engagement in “meaningful [...] activities which are required or desired to fulfil the role of the school pupil within or around the school context. This includes classroom learning, social relationships, and school-wide activities”. Inclusive school participation also involves social elements, which Koster and colleagues (2009) characterise by four central themes: friendships/relationships, positive interactions, subjective perceptions, and acceptance by classmates (see also Bossaert et al., 2013).

In recent years, many countries have intensified efforts to promote the inclusion of students with disabilities in mainstream education, following the ratification of the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities in 2006 (United Nations, 2006). In Germany, this has led to a growing number of students with hearing loss attending mainstream schools; previously educated predominantly in specialised schools for the Deaf, more than half are now enrolled in mainstream schools (Kultusministerkonferenz, 2024). Despite a push for inclusive education, students with hearing loss face barriers to full participation arising from the complex spoken language environments and perceptual challenges (Tomblin et al., 2015; Wie et al., 2020), which affect their social, personal, and educational lives (Luckner & Movahedazarhouli, 2019; Schwab et al., 2019; Tsach & Most, 2016).

Understanding the factors that contribute to successful school participation requires including the perspectives of students themselves; accordingly, the present study investigates their subjective experiences in mainstream schools.

1.1. Participation within the ICF framework

The International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF; World Health Organization, 2001) conceptualises functioning as a dynamic interaction between health conditions and contextual factors (Maxwell et al., 2018). It distinguishes environmental (e.g., school setting) and personal factors (e.g., coping style) from functioning and disability, which encompass body functions and structures (e.g., auditory system) as well as activities and participation (e.g., classroom engagement, social interactions). Applied to students with hearing loss, the ICF highlights that participation is not determined solely by impairment, but by a complex interplay of body functions, activity limitations, environmental supports or barriers, and individual characteristics such as motivation, self-confidence, self-efficacy, and social skills.

1.2. Challenges for students with hearing loss in mainstream schools

Classroom communication is often characterised by rapid speaker changes and overlapping speech, requiring students to process auditory input from multiple sources, focus selectively on relevant information, and ignore distractions (Cerney, 2007; Preisler et al., 2005). Comprehension is further challenged when classmates speak quickly or softly—especially during group interactions—or are unwilling to repeat their statements (Preisler et al., 2005). Consequently, students with hearing loss are more likely to experience listening fatigue and concentration difficulties, which can negatively affect memory retention and information processing (Brännström et al., 2019; Hornsby et al., 2021). Poor acoustic conditions, such as high levels of background noise and reverberation, further impair speech comprehension and learning for all students (Dockrell & Shield, 2006; Klatt et al., 2013; Mattys et al., 2012; Sato & Bradley, 2008).

Although personal hearing technology, such as hearing aids, cochlear implants, and FM systems, have advanced, students with hearing loss continue to experience listening difficulties (Krijger et al., 2020), partly because assistive technologies such as FM systems or soundfield amplification systems are inconsistently integrated and supported by teachers (Takala & Sume, 2018). Also, in contrast to specialised schools for the Deaf, which often feature smaller class sizes and enhanced auditory and technological setups, mainstream schools frequently lack adequate environmental adaptations (Crandell & Smaldino, 2000).

Even though students with hearing loss in mainstream schools often demonstrate comparable academic abilities (Tsach & Most, 2016) and a similar level of engagement to their peers with typical hearing (Borders et al., 2010; Todorov et al., 2021), they frequently depend on individualised support such as repeated instructions, teacher prompting, and visual cues like eye contact (Borders et al., 2010; Tsach & Most, 2016). Persistent difficulties remain in understanding teachers and classmates, particularly in noisy environments or group interactions (Borders et al., 2010; Edmondson & Howe, 2019; Hatamizadeh et al., 2008; Punch & Hyde, 2011).

A mixed-methods study by Todorov and colleagues (2021, 2022) found considerable variability in engagement. While many students performed similarly to peers with typical hearing, others reported substantial challenges from adverse classroom acoustics, multi-step instructions, and limitations of assistive technologies. Interviews revealed emotional strain, listening fatigue, and a heightened need for teacher and peer support, but also resilience through coping strategies such as strategic seating and visual orientation.

Social participation remains a key dimension of school participation, yet remains particularly vulnerable for students with hearing loss. Some report acceptance within supportive peer groups (Edmondson & Howe, 2019; Powers, 2002; Punch & Hyde, 2005). Positive peer relationships fostered belonging, while awareness among teachers and classmates and access to assistive technologies further supported social participation (Edmondson & Howe, 2019; Eriks-Brophy et al., 2006; Jarvis, 2003). Individual factors such as self-advocacy, communication skills, and confidence also facilitated social participation (Edmondson & Howe, 2019; Eriks-Brophy et al., 2006; Punch & Hyde, 2011). Yet, other students experienced reduced social acceptance, reporting insensitive comments or

feeling of difference (Edmondson & Howe, 2019; Israelite, 2002). Schwab and colleagues (2019) found that while friendships within class were maintained, many preferred peers who were also assessed for special educational needs.

Notably, much of the existing evidence comes from contexts where dedicated Deaf support, peer communities, and targeted resources are available, which may limit transferability to many mainstream settings where students with hearing loss are often the only one in their class and specialised support is limited. Moreover, most studies have focused on describing challenges rather than actively involving students in shaping solutions.

1.3. The current study

The present study addresses this gap by exploring the subjective experiences of participation among students with hearing loss in mainstream schools. Importantly, students were not only asked to describe the barriers they encounter, but also to provide their own recommendations for improving participation in academic and social school life. This direct involvement highlights students' perspectives as essential for developing both practical and policy-level strategies to foster inclusive schooling.

The following research questions guided this study:

1. How do students with hearing loss experience participation in mainstream schools?
2. What specific recommendations for improving their school environment do students with hearing loss report?

By focusing on student's lived experiences and their direct suggestions, this study aims to deepen our understanding of the conditions that promote or hinder meaningful participation in mainstream school settings.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Design

A qualitative, descriptive research approach was chosen to capture the complexity and depth of student's individual perspectives. This approach allows for close engagement with the original data and supports the interpretation of experiences from the participants' point of view (Creswell & Creswell, 2023). This study was grounded in a constructivist paradigm, which holds that individuals construct meaning through social interaction and subjective interpretation. These meanings are inherently diverse, context-dependent, and should be explored from the participants' perspectives (Creswell & Creswell, 2023).

Table 1
Participant characteristics.

Participant	Gender	Age at interview	Degree of hearing loss	Laterality	Hearing device(s)
01	F	8;4	Mild	Bilateral	Bilateral HAS
02	M	13;0	Profound	Bilateral	Bilateral CIs
03	M	7;9	Profound	Bilateral	CI+HA
04	M	16;6	Moderate to severe	Unilateral	Unilateral HA
05	F	8;0	Moderate	Bilateral	Bilateral HAS
06	M	9;0	Moderate to severe	Unilateral	Unilateral HA
07	F	12;2	Severe to profound	Bilateral	Bilateral HAS
09	F	13;6	Profound	Unilateral	Unilateral CI
10	F	13;11	Profound	Bilateral	Bilateral CIs
11	M	11;10	Severe	Bilateral	Bilateral HAS
12	F	9;5	Severe to profound	Unilateral	Unilateral HA
13	F	8;3	Moderate to severe	Bilateral	Bilateral HAS
14	F	7;4	Moderate to severe	Bilateral	Bilateral HAS
15	M	13;9	Mild	Bilateral	Bilateral HAS
16	M	9;4	Moderate to severe	Unilateral	Unilateral HA
17	M	13;10	Profound	Bilateral	Bilateral HAS
18	M	8;9	Moderate to severe	Unilateral	Unilateral HA
19	F	7;1	Profound	Unilateral	Unilateral HA
20	F	9;9	Profound	Bilateral	Bilateral CIs
21	F	8;3	Mild	Bilateral	Bilateral HAS
22	F	15;1	Moderate to severe	Bilateral	Bilateral HAS
23	M	9;11	Moderate to severe	Bilateral	Bilateral HAS
24	M	13;6	Severe	Bilateral	Bilateral HAS
25	M	11;8	Moderate to severe	Bilateral	Bilateral HAS
26	F	9;11	Mild to moderate	Bilateral	Bilateral HAS
27	M	13;2	Moderate to severe	Bilateral	Bilateral HAS

Note. HA = hearing aid; CI = cochlear implant.

2.2. Data collection

Semi-structured interviews were conducted using an interview guide (see appendix A) based on [Todorov and colleagues \(2022\)](#), covering classroom engagement, including facilitating and hindering factors, and support from teachers and peers. Additional items from [Schwab and colleagues \(2019\)](#) focused on social participation within the classroom. Further topics included the learning environment—particularly acoustics, didactic settings, and the use of assistive technology. Follow-up questions allowed for deeper exploration of each theme. This approach provided a flexible structure while enabling participants to share their experiences in their own words ([Adams, 2015](#)).

All interviews were conducted in spoken German by the first author, a doctoral researcher with a master's degree in special needs education, who was previously unknown to the participants. Interviews took place in a quiet, one-on-one setting, either in a separate room at the student's mainstream school or in a university office room. Interviews were audio-recorded using a digital voice recorder (Olympus linear PCM).

The interviews typically took 20–30 min. Interviews were anonymised using participant codes. Transcripts were generated verbatim using f4 software and reviewed for accuracy by the first author and a student research assistant.

Ethical approval was granted by the central ethics committee of the Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg. Participation was voluntary, and written informed consent was obtained from all students and their legal guardians. To thank them for their participation, each student received a small gift.

2.3. Participants

To be included in this study, students had to meet the following criteria: (1) a diagnosed of unilateral or bilateral hearing loss (>25 dBHL), (2) enrolment in grades 2–10 of mainstream schooling, and (3) spoken German as their primary mode of communication.

A purposeful sampling strategy was used to recruit participants likely to provide rich insights into everyday school life with hearing loss, enabling the collection of experience-based, in-depth data from a specific subgroup ([Creswell & Creswell, 2023](#)). Participants were recruited via schools and an advertisement in a regional newspaper. In total, 27 German-speaking students aged 7;1 to 16;6 years ($M = 11;0$ years, 13 female, 14 male) took part in the study (see [Table 1](#)). One student was excluded due to an auditory processing and perception disorder.

The sample, consisting of 26 students with variation in age and degree of hearing loss, supported strong information power, considering the focused aim and the use of semi-structured interviews ([Creswell & Creswell, 2023](#); [Malterud et al., 2016](#)).

According to parental reports (via questionnaires), the average age of hearing loss diagnosis was 3;1 years, with hearing loss severity ranging from mild to profound. Four children used cochlear implants, twenty-one used hearing aids, and one used both. Seven students had unilateral and 19 had bilateral hearing loss. The average age for the initiation of intervention was 3;4 years.

All students attended mainstream schools, spreading across 22 different institutions in Lower Saxony. While mobile support services for students with hearing loss are available in the region to advise schools and teachers, no specialist teacher for hearing loss was present in regular class.

2.4. Data analysis

Interview data were analysed thematically following [Braun and Clarke's \(2006\)](#) guidelines using MAXQDA ([VERBI Software, 2024](#)). After initial familiarization with the data, the first author coded the interviews using the ICF framework as a guiding structure. Codes were organised within the overarching categories of environmental factors and personal factors following [Van Den Heuij and colleagues \(2022\)](#). Within the ICF framework, environmental factors were analysed across four subdomains relevant to this study: attitudes, behaviour, learning environment, and technology. Attitudes refer to beliefs and perceptions held by individuals, while behaviours describe observable actions and interactions resulting from these attitudes. Technology includes assistive devices, such as

Fig. 1. Themes and subthemes related to the school participation of students with hearing loss.

soundfield amplification systems. The learning environment includes the physical, social, and organisational contexts in which learning occurs. As the ICF does not provide a detailed categorisation of personal factors, the corresponding themes were developed inductively from the interview data. To ensure rigour, themes and subcodes were discussed collaboratively among the authors, refining the theme labels, and resolving any discrepancies through collaborative discussion until consensus was achieved.

3. Results

The thematic analysis with a focus on environmental and personal factors identified eight main themes: four related to environmental factors and four to personal factors, each with corresponding subthemes, reflecting student's subjective experiences and perceptions of their participation in mainstream school settings. In relation to the second research questions, students' recommendations for improving their school environment were coded and aligned with the identified themes related to environmental factors Fig. 1.

3.1. Environmental factors

The analysis of the interviews revealed four main themes related to environmental factors supporting or hindering students' school participation, including *attitudes and relationships*, *behaviours*, *learning environment*, and *technology*.

3.1.1. Attitudes and relationships

Participants consistently emphasised the critical role of attitudes held by teachers and peers in influencing their sense of belonging and participation. Empathy, respect, and awareness were key facilitators, fostering involvement. Conversely, misunderstanding or stigma could pose significant barriers. *Teachers' attitudes* emerged as particularly influential. Most students described their teachers as "engaged" (P04), "sensitive" (P15), and "attentive" (P26) to individual needs, acknowledging the impact of hearing loss by noticing "when something wasn't clear to us" (P10). In some cases, this attentiveness extended to independent learning and commitment:

"My former class teacher was so kind and really engaged with the topic, she even did her own research on it." (P02)

In contrast, other students experienced a lack of awareness and understanding, which undermined their sense of participation. Some teachers "don't understand that you really can't follow" (P17) in lessons and assumed inattention rather than communication barriers, reflecting misconceptions such as believing hearing aids allow to "hear just like the other kids" (P07). Other students experienced stigmatising remarks. For example, one student recalled insensitive comments during a class presentation referencing disabilities:

"Then the teacher, again an older one, said: 'Oh, were there kids with disabilities like you?'" (P04)

In relation to the second research question, students expressed a desire for greater "understanding" (P02) and "openness to student perspectives" (P17). They suggested that increased teacher "awareness" (P06) and "knowledge" (P07) about hearing loss would enhance inclusive support.

Classmates' attitudes strongly influenced students' experiences of involvement. Many participants reported positive and respectful relationships with classmates who treated them "just like anyone else" (P20) and involved them in group activities. Some classmates showed attentiveness, for instance by noticing "when it gets too loud for me" (P25), demonstrating sensitivity to their hearing needs. At the same time, others exhibited a lack of respect and recounted moments of resentment or insensitive remarks regarding accommodations, such as:

"They said they'd rather have a cochlear implant and get those kinds of accommodation." (P09)

Despite these challenges, many students experienced positive peer relationships and inclusion in social activities, exemplified by simple moments of playing together:

"Everyone comes to me, and then we just play together." (P16)

Nevertheless, occasional teasing and exclusion persisted, reinforcing feelings of difference:

"There are people who don't understand at all, who are extra loud or make sure you can't hear well." (P15)

As a result, students with hearing loss wished to be treated "equally" (P06) and recommended greater "awareness" (P25) and "acceptance" (P20) from their classmates to improve participation.

3.1.2. Behaviours

Students also highlighted how concrete behaviours of teachers and peers influenced accessibility and inclusivity of the learning environments. *Supportive teacher behaviour* included effective classroom management, particularly regulating noise and enforcing clear routines, which created calmer, more manageable settings:

"Miss [Name] always rings a bell. Then everyone has to sit down and be quiet." (P06)

In addition, many students highlighted the importance of visual communication strategies for ensuring comprehension. Facing the class while speaking, articulating clearly, maintaining eye contact were essential for making spoken language more accessible. One

student noted how helpful it was when teachers “look into the classroom [...] so that you can read their lips” (P02). In contrast, comprehension is difficult when teachers simultaneously “start writing on the board and then begin to mumble or speak more slowly and quietly” (P17) at the same time, reducing audibility and making lipreading more challenging.

Another important supportive aspect was the consistent implementation of accommodations, particularly during tests. For example, one student noted that listening tasks were “not included in my grade, because I sometimes have trouble understanding it—especially often in English” (P10).

Addressing the second research question, students wished that teachers would be “more responsive to individual children” (P17), use “diverse teaching approaches” (P04), give “more time to respond” (P09), and “encourage to ask questions” (P18).

Classmate behaviour varied but impacted participation and communication. Many students described helpful classmates who would repeat instructions or explain tasks “when I don’t understand something in class because of the acoustics” (P02).

Some peers even took on an advocacy role, intervening when the learning environment became too noisy. One student shared how their classmates defended them, saying “There’s usually someone in our group who says we should be quiet for a moment” (P16). At the same time, inconsistent communication practices among classmates could be frustrating. While some classmates adapted their behaviour by speaking more “clearly” (P27), others “mumbled” (P05), “shouted” (P26), or spoke “quietly” (P22), making it difficult to follow. One student summed up the situation:

“It’s normal that it’s loud [...] and then others speak really quietly.” (P19)

Students recommended that better classroom management can positively influence classmates’ behaviour and enhance interaction and communication in the classroom.

3.1.3. Learning environment

The physical and acoustic conditions of the school environment influenced students’ learning experiences.

Regarding the *acoustic conditions in the classroom*, many students reported generally good audibility and comprehension in their classrooms, while most described high background noise levels due to overlapping conversations, increasing the mental and listening effort required to follow the lesson. One student described this strain:

“It takes a lot of concentration when you have to focus on one person the whole time while everyone else is talking around you.” (P17)

Moreover, auditory overload resulted in increased processing demands and feelings of communication insecurity for some students:

“Sometimes I need to process things first before I can answer. But that might take a bit.” (P09)

Seating arrangements had a direct impact on auditory and visual access. Many students preferred front-row seats, allowing for “better hearing” (P14) and “lip-reading” (P02). In addition, other supportive setups such as “sitting next to a friend” (P06) or having “swivel chairs” (P03), enabled students to turn toward the speaker, maintain visual contact, and better understand teacher’s speech. However, individual preferences varied. For some students, sitting in the front was distracting, especially when surrounded by movement and noise:

“I’d always turn around when I heard something and then I’d be distracted. [...] And it’s different in the back. There, I can work on my tasks better.” (P17)

Group and partner work posed significant challenges. While quieter settings were manageable, “overlapping conversations” (P25) and “unclear speech” (P09), led to increased listening effort. As one student described the cognitive load of filtering relevant speech in group works:

“In regular lessons, the teacher says something, asks something, and a student answers. But during group work, everyone mumbles or talks to each other.” (P04)

The ability to “move to other rooms” (P01) with quieter environments for group activities was described as helpful in reducing listening effort.

Subject-specific challenges were notable, particularly in foreign language lessons. Fast speech and unfamiliar pronunciation hindered comprehension. For instance, one student shared:

“My Spanish teacher [...] is a native speaker, and she talks a bit faster, a bit differently, and somehow lip-reading doesn’t really work with her.” (P02)

A few students reported challenges “pronouncing foreign words” (P09), especially, when unfamiliar phonemes and a lack of auditory feedback made self-monitoring difficult. Additionally, the frequent use of audio recordings such as “digital listening exercises” (P02) often complicated comprehension due to poor audio quality, fast speech rates, and overlapping sounds.

Common school spaces, including “cafeterias” (P20), “hallways” (P03), “toilettes” (P26) were typically perceived as noisy and challenging for speech intelligibility. Subject-specific classrooms, such as “science” (P15) or “art rooms” (P09), were also often not specifically adapted and equipped with technology for students with hearing loss. Reactions to sport halls were ambivalent. Some students found the reverberation helpful as “the voices get louder” (P12). However, others experienced the same acoustics as disturbing if “the teacher is shouting and it echoes. [...] I do hear that the person is saying something. Just not what they are saying” (P09).

To address the second research question, students proposed practical changes like “listening breaks” (P04), “reasonable adjustments” (P02)—for example extra time or reading instead of listening tasks in tests—to cope with challenges in foreign language lessons, “individual solutions” (P17) regarding seating positions and opportunities to work in quieter settings during group work.

3.1.4. Technology

Assistive hearing technologies, such as FM and soundfield amplification systems, were central aspects of students’ everyday school experience. Two main subcategories emerged: *management and responsibilities* and *use and availability*.

Management and responsibility of assistive technology often rested disproportionately on students themselves. Many described how they frequently “reminding” (P14) teachers to use or activate devices.

In some cases, students even took on the role of training new teachers. A few even encountered outright resistance and a lack of willingness to engage with the technology as one student reported: “When I handed over the microphones and other things I needed, some teachers, mostly older ones, just said, ‘No I’m not doing that’” (P04).

Where available and properly used, assistive systems improved audibility and intelligibility for the whole class:

“I think through the microphones, because it’s louder then, others can understand them [quiet speaker] better too.” (P09)

However, “inconsistent” (P22) or “inappropriate” (P07) use, undermined these potential benefits. A common complaint was that teachers “often forget to mute it [the microphone]” (P17), which “distracts” (P10) students. Constant exposure to amplified voices was another source of fatigue, “because having the teacher’s voice in my ear the whole time gets annoying” (P22). Auditory overload also occurred when multiple voices overlapped like “if a classmate speaks into the microphone, I hear but then can’t really hear the teacher anymore” (P27). Teachers raising their voices, e.g., when disciplining students, or yelling of classmates were also factors causing “discomfort” (P17).

Other barriers included inappropriate or playful misuse of microphones by peers:

“Some kids [...] fool around with it and talk into it, and I hear it all directly in my ear.” (P01)

Beyond classroom use, managing the devices themselves was sometimes described as stressful and time-consuming, particularly during transitions:

“You have to pack up all your devices, check if there are scratches or anything, and that takes times and makes you feel stressed. It also cuts into your break time a lot.” (P02)

Based on the challenges the students experienced with assistive devices, many students concluded that “improved use by teachers” (P09) could enhance classroom participation, as “correct usage” (P07) supports better understanding of lessons. To achieve this positive effect, it is important that teachers use the devices “consistently” (P10) to avoid disrupting students’ learning.

3.2. Personal factors

Four themes emerged including *coping strategies*, *subjective experience of participation*, *experienced challenges related to hearing loss*, and *avoidance strategies* that reflect aspects of students’ personal resources and lived experiences in managing participation-related challenges.

3.2.1. Coping strategies

Students with hearing loss employed a variety of coping strategies to manage communication and participation challenges in mainstream classrooms. These include behavioural adaptations, communication tactics, and self-advocacy efforts, reflecting both proactive and avoidant forms of engagement.

Self-advocacy emerged as a key competence. Students emphasised the importance of clearly communicating their needs to others and actively seeking clarification when missing or misunderstanding verbal information, such as asking classmates to reduce noise or to “speak louder” (P20) or to “repeat it” (P05).

However, this was often accompanied by social discomfort. Some students described feeling burdensome when repeatedly seeking support from peers or teachers:

“It’s annoying to always bother my seatmates and ask what we were supposed to do. Because it also kind of disturbs the other classmates.” (P26)

In some cases, students masked their misunderstanding by avoiding drawing attention to their difficulties:

“Sometimes I just smile, even though I didn’t understand.” (P09)

To compensate for missed verbal input, several students described adaptive behaviour such as “watched what the others were doing and just copied them” (P22). Other commonly used strategies included physically “repositioning” themselves in the classroom like turning to the speaking person to improve their ability to follow lessons.

To cope with environmental barriers, especially background noise, several students responded by adjusting their hearing devices themselves, like turning “them [hearing aids] off when it gets too loud” (P21), which regulates auditory input and reduces listening fatigue.

Importantly, students also spoke about the broader emotional process of accepting their hearing loss and developing a positive

attitude toward this. Most of the students approached this with openness and confidence as one student put it, the key is to “accept it early on” (P15).

However, not all students reached this level of acceptance. Some expressed frustration with or strong rejection of their devices, showing deeper emotional conflicts:

“I think cochlear implants are awful. I don’t think people really know how bad it actually is.” (P09)

3.2.2. Subjective experience of participation

Participants shared diverse and often ambivalent perspectives on what participation in mainstream classrooms feels like. Many described that participation as inherently more demanding for them, requiring additional effort and constant self-monitoring. One student reflected openly on the unequal conditions in everyday classroom interactions:

“I’d have it easier if I could hear like the others [...]. I wouldn’t always have to ask again.” (P25)

Certain classroom formats, especially those involving fast-paced and competitive learning formats, were reported as challenging. One student recounted their difficulties during a math-based classroom game, leading to structural exclusion in a classroom activity:

“One person reads from a slip of paper, and I stand in a corner. And whoever answers first makes the guess. But the person who reads always speaks to quietly, and I don’t hear the math task. And it’s a competition, so I can’t move on to the next corner. I just don’t hear it.” (P14)

Yet, despite such barriers, many students expressed a strong sense of resilience and agency. Rather than withdrawing entirely, they focused on the elements where they could take part:

“I do the tasks I understand” (P14).

3.2.3. Experienced challenges related to hearing loss

Students reported interrelated challenges in their everyday school lives, affecting them emotionally, physically, cognitively, and socially.

Emotionally, many students described persistent feelings of vulnerability, low self-esteem and a fear of social exclusion. A few students reported being misjudged by peers, particularly the fear that “people in my class think I just want attention” (P09). Another added the fear “of being laughed at when the ear looks a bit strange or if there’s a beeping sound [from the hearing device]” (P18). Such social insecurities contribute to internalised emotional distress, often accompanied by feelings of unfairness or resignations as one student stated:

“I just feel sad that I have this. Why was I born with it, of all people?” (P09)

Beyond emotional strain, many students reported heightened physical sensitivity, such as being “more sensitive to noise” (P24). The effort required to process auditory information throughout the day often leads to fatigue and physical discomfort as noise can cause “headaches” (P25) and “ear pain” (P09).

Listening fatigue emerged as a recurring theme:

“The longer the day goes on, the harder it gets. You start the day fresh, but over time it gets exhausting to keep focusing, especially when you want to follow the teacher and keep up with your grades.” (P17)

Others highlighted the disparity between their effort and the ease with which hearing peers process information, as “others just half-listen and still catch everything. I really try hard to understand everything” (P15).

Rapid speech or unclear instructions also lead to misunderstandings, as one participant noted:

“If the teacher speaks too fast and says a page number, I might hear the wrong number and do the wrong task.” (P15)

The cumulative effect of emotional and auditory challenges often translated into academic difficulties. Tasks that rely on auditory input—such as dictations—are particularly problematic:

“I always got bad grades in dictations. I still don’t write everything correctly.” (P25)

Others reported on moments of speech-related anxiety:

“Because I’m afraid that I might say something wrong. And then I first have to figure out what the question was again. And repeat everything. And then I need a bit more time, but then the teacher just picks someone who’s good in class instead.” (P09)

3.2.4. Avoidance strategies

While many students demonstrated active engagement, others reported on instances of avoidance behaviours to manage the social risks of disclosing or addressing their needs.

Fear of being seen as annoying or different and the desire to maintain peer relationships often led some students to tolerate classroom barriers rather than disrupt social dynamics:

“Sometimes I get this feeling that they should just be quiet. I’d really like to tell them, but I don’t want to come across as annoying” (P09)

Similarly, some students avoided using assistive systems due to discomfort with perceived special treatment as this outweighed the benefits of improved access:

“This extra thing at the beginning of every class, like telling the teacher, for example, that they could use the FM system or something, that’s kind of annoying too. [...] I just preferred it without, honestly.” (P17)

In more explicit terms, fear of social exclusion and negative peer judgment shaped participation choices. The anticipation of being singled out as ‘other’ led some to conceal their hearing loss or avoid requesting accommodations. One student described how being seen as different could threaten their social belonging:

“Because the others quickly start thinking, like ‘Ugh, no, he gets special treatment, I don’t want anything to do with him because he’s so different.’” (P02)

Finally, some older students described how their support needs had shifted throughout their school attendance. While they recalled a stronger need for “one-on-one assistance” (P04) during their early school years, one student described how the increase of “self-directed learning tasks” (P17) in secondary school helped him reduce the need of having to hear “everything the teacher said” (P17).

4. Discussion

This qualitative study explored the lived experiences of students with hearing loss in mainstream schools, focusing on how they perceive school participation as well as their recommendations for improvement. The findings reveal an interplay of multiple environmental and personal factors that can either facilitate or hinder students’ participation in school.

1) How do students with hearing loss experience participation in mainstream schools?

All participants in this study were the only students with hearing loss in their respective classes, which often influenced their experiences of participation and belonging. One of the most reported influences on participation was the role of interpersonal dynamics in relation to attitudes and behaviours of teachers and classmates. Positive participation experiences were often associated with teachers and classmates who demonstrated an open and supportive attitude, fostered engagement through effective classroom management, and adapted their communication styles to meet students’ needs. These findings align with previous research emphasising the importance of peer support during lessons, as it fosters a sense of belonging and encourages active participation in classroom activities (Eriks-Brophy et al., 2006; Todorov et al., 2022). Additionally, the results are consistent with previous research showing that most teachers generally hold positive attitudes towards the inclusion of students with hearing loss in mainstream schools (Keerthan K et al., 2025). However, these studies, as well as our findings, indicate that students with hearing loss often require more individualised support, such as an increased use of non-verbal cues, including eye contact (Borders et al., 2010; Hatamizadeh et al., 2008; Punch & Hyde, 2011; Tsach & Most, 2016). Moreover, the students in this study emphasised the importance of consistent implementation of accommodations for enabling them to keep up with their classmates, achieve good grades, and avoid educational disadvantages. At the same time, some students were hesitant about receiving such “special treatment”, expressing concerns that these accommodations could reinforce perceptions of being different and potentially increase the risk of social exclusion by their classmates. It is therefore essential that teachers consider the individual perspectives and needs of students, involving them actively in identifying and shaping appropriate support strategies.

In contrast to students reports of helpful interactions, some students reported that certain teachers and classmates demonstrated limited awareness and engagement. Instances were described in which teachers or classmates made insensitive comments about hearing loss and/or disabilities, showed low engagement to consistently adapt their teaching and behaviour. In some cases, teachers appeared to assume that the use of hearing devices fully resolves students’ communication difficulties, indicating a limited understanding of the broader impacts of hearing loss. These experiences emphasise the need to improve teacher awareness and knowledge about hearing loss and its effects through targeted professional training (e.g., special education teacher), as strengthening teachers’ competence in educating students with hearing loss can promote more inclusive and responsive teaching practices (Edmondson & Howe, 2019; Keerthan K et al., 2025).

Regarding social participation, nearly all students reported having friendships in class, feeling accepted and included in their peer group. However, a number of students experienced fewer positive interactions and encountered teasing, felt excluded in social activities, or sensed irritation from peers due to a perceived “special treatment”. These findings align with earlier research suggesting that while many students with hearing loss are socially accepted and develop positive peer relationships (Edmondson & Howe, 2019), some students continue to face an increased risk of lower social participation (Punch & Hyde, 2011; Schwab et al., 2019). It also highlights the importance of classroom teachers in fostering peer relationships between students with hearing loss and their classmates (Todorov et al., 2022).

The physical and acoustic learning environment emerged as another key factor affecting participation. While some classrooms were perceived as acoustically manageable, background noise, overlapping conversations, as well as subject-specific rooms and outside school areas emerged as major challenges, as poor acoustics impede speech perception, increase listening effort (Mattys et al., 2012; Sato & Bradley, 2008) and can affect school success (Dockrell & Shield, 2006; Klatt et al., 2013). As an additional aspect, the students

in this study pointed to auditory overload as a factor that not only heightened processing demands but also led to feelings of communication insecurity. Consequently, auditory overload and the associated feelings of communication insecurity may function as barriers to students' active participation during lessons. These challenges are especially evident during group and partner work. [Todorov and colleagues \(2022\)](#) attribute this to increased background noise from simultaneous group discussions and the fast-paced, dynamic nature of such interactions, making it harder to follow discussions and actively engage in classroom interactions ([Edmondson & Howe, 2019](#); [Preisler et al., 2005](#); [Punch & Hyde, 2011](#)).

The negative impact of poor acoustic conditions in classrooms and high background noise on speech intelligibility can be reduced with assistive listening technologies ([Mealings, 2022](#)). When classrooms were equipped with these devices and they were appropriately used, students noted that these technologies improved their own access to spoken information and enhanced speech clarity for the entire class. However, the consistent and effective use of these tools depended heavily on the teacher's willingness and competence. Students often had to assume responsibility for initiating or managing device use, such as reminding teachers to activate or deactivate systems or distributing handheld microphones to peers. In some cases, devices were forgotten, misused, or generated auditory overload, leading to frustration and sometimes discomfort. Such experiences align with previous research documenting that devices were often underused or poorly integrated into classroom routines ([Takala & Sume, 2018](#); [Todorov et al., 2022](#)).

Within this study, subject-specific challenges were particularly evident in foreign language lessons, which often rely heavily on oral input and auditory processing. Students described difficulties in decoding unfamiliar pronunciation and phonemes as significantly impeding their comprehension and limiting their ability to participate actively in these lessons. Teachers should be aware that foreign language lessons can impose increased cognitive and perceptual demands on students with hearing loss. Therefore, ensuring visual access to both classmates and the teacher is especially critical in these subjects.

In addition to external conditions, the students in this study demonstrated a wide range of personal strategies to manage participation challenges. Many students showed strong self-advocacy skills and adaptability, using techniques such as lip-reading, orientating toward the speaker, or requesting repetition or clarification. Moreover, some students described adjusting or temporarily turning off their hearing devices as an important strategy to cope with noisy settings. These proactive behaviours reflect resilience and align with prior findings that emphasise the importance of self-advocacy as a coping strategy for students with hearing loss ([Todorov et al., 2022](#)) and to foster this competence, particularly among students with lower levels of self-advocacy who experience difficulties in managing participation-related challenges.

At the same time, the findings reveal the reliance on individual responsibility in the implementation of inclusive practices. Students frequently described a tension between asserting their needs and avoiding social discomfort. They often attempted to avoid drawing attention to their hearing loss and the associated challenges, in order to prevent being perceived as different ([Punch & Hyde, 2005](#)). This hesitation also extended to the use of hearing devices. Such rejection may not only reflect dissatisfaction with the device itself but also deeper emotional tensions around identity, visibility, and perceived normalcy. While some participants embraced their hearing loss as part of their self-concepts, others struggled with stigma and discomfort associated with it. The results show a complex emotional tension between the desire for social inclusion and the need for support, with students often prioritising social acceptance over seeking assistance. This may be linked to individual differences in self-perception, as some students expressed confidence and acceptance, others experienced frustration, identity conflicts, and feelings of otherness. In this context, disengagement or avoidance should not be seen as a lack of motivation, but rather as a protective strategy aimed at maintaining self-esteem and social acceptance.

Listening fatigue was another recurring theme. Many students reported mental exhausting from sustained effort to follow lessons, especially in fast-paced or heavily auditory-based teaching. Such fatigue affected concentration and learning ([Brännström et al., 2019](#); [Hornsby et al., 2021](#)), making it harder to participate in lessons, particularly at the end of the school day. Furthermore, some students reported that poorer comprehension led to speech-related anxiety, because of the cognitive load from having to reinterpret questions and repeat responses and the fear of giving incorrect answers. Such dynamics may contribute to reduced classroom participation and highlight the need for supportive strategies that address both comprehension challenges and speech-related anxiety, while allowing adequate response time.

Finally, many students emphasised that school participation is inherently more demanding for them, requiring ongoing effort and constant self-monitoring, with most of them reflecting on the unequal conditions they face in everyday classroom interactions.

2) What specific recommendations for improvement do students with hearing loss report?

In response to the second research question, students provided clear and experience-based suggestions for improving their participation in mainstream schools. Across interviews, a central theme was the need for greater sensitivity and awareness from teachers and classmates. Students wished to be perceived as equally competent as their hearing peers rather than "different" from them and expressed a desire to be listened to and taken seriously. They called for teachers to develop a deeper understanding of hearing loss and to implement practical accommodations in their teachings. These included facing the class while speaking, articulating clearly, repeating instructions, and fostering a calm, structured learning environment. Such basic teaching strategies (e.g., effective classroom management, clear speech) were reported as particularly beneficial for students with hearing loss ([Todorov et al., 2022](#)). In addition to general teaching strategies, students advocated for more differentiated instruction and flexible teaching methods. They emphasised the need for time to process information and opportunities to ask questions without pressure. Providing individual response time and clear task explanations was perceived as supportive for effective learning. Another key recommendation was improved classroom and noise management. Many students reported that high background noise made it difficult to concentrate and follow classroom interactions. To reduce this barrier, they suggested separating disruptive classmates, regulating classroom discussions, and maintaining calm, respectful atmosphere.

Also, students expressed the need for teachers to take more responsibility for the consistent and correct use of assistive listening technologies. This supports earlier findings by [Todorov and colleagues \(2022\)](#), who attribute limited use of handheld microphones to a lack of practical training and difficulties in integrating them into everyday classroom practice. Students explicitly called for targeted teacher training and greater accountability, to ensure these technologies function as intended and are regularly used.

Students further proposed practical changes to the learning environment. To manage acoustic challenges, they advocated seating closer to the teacher for improving auditory and visual access, with front-row seating speech intelligibility and lip-reading ([Crandell & Smaldino, 2000](#); [Todorov et al., 2022](#)). However, participant preferences varied, with some finding front-row placement distracting due to an overload of visual or auditory stimuli, underscoring the importance of addressing individual needs. Scheduled listening breaks may serve to mitigate this effect. Such breaks were suggested as a way to reduce listening fatigue and supported sustained attention throughout the school day. Additionally, access to quieter spaces during group work was seen as beneficial for maintaining focus and engagement.

An additional insight emerged regarding the shifting of students' needs over school stages, suggesting the importance of individualised and dynamic support systems that adjust to students' growing competencies and changing classroom demands.

Taken together, these student-driven suggestions point to a need for schools to adopt a more responsive, learner-centred approach recognising the specific support needs of students with hearing loss without compromising their sense of belonging and participation.

4.1. Limitations and future research

This qualitative study explored the perspectives of students with hearing loss aged 7 to 16 years regarding their participation in mainstream schools. While the findings offer valuable insights into lived experiences, some limitations should be considered. The sample consisted of a heterogeneous group of students from various schools and grade levels in Lower Saxony. Participation was voluntary, which may have resulted in a sample biased toward those with stronger support systems, higher confidence, or more positive experiences. Non-random, purposive sampling was necessary to access this specific and relatively small population, though it may have introduced sampling bias. Broad inclusion criteria were used to capture a range of experiences. However, all participants were able to comprehend and express themselves in spoken German, limiting findings to a specific subgroup of students with hearing loss in mainstream schools. Additionally, the study was confined to one federal state and specific school context, which may limit generalisability. Regional differences in the role and availability of visiting teachers of the Deaf, funding, and assistive technology use could influence students' participation experiences.

Further research should aim to include the perspectives of teachers, parents, and classmates to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the dynamics that shape participation. Comparing viewpoints may help to uncover mismatches in expectations or highlight areas where increased communication and training are needed. Longitudinal studies could also provide insight into how experiences of participation evolve across different developmental stages and educational transitions.

4.2. Practical implications

The findings of this study highlight several key areas for improving the participation of students with hearing loss in mainstream classrooms. While many students demonstrated self-advocacy skills, not all students are equally equipped to advocate for themselves. It is therefore essential that schools, teachers, and special educational needs staff provide targeted support and training to help students to develop strong self-advocacy skills that empower students to express their needs and to manage participation challenges more effectively.

Moreover, teachers played a central role in shaping participation. Their awareness of hearing loss, their ability to apply supportive communication strategies, managing classroom noise, and their consistent use of assistive listening devices were key facilitators of participation. Ongoing professional development in inclusive practices (e.g., teaching strategies, device management) is therefore crucial. Furthermore, teachers hold a particular responsibility in fostering peer awareness and facilitating behaviours that support inclusion within the classroom context.

Finally, collaboration between all stakeholders (students, teachers, parents, and special education staff) is vital to ensure that accommodations are consistently implemented and adapted to individual needs. A shared understanding of participation barriers and a commitment to responsive practices can help foster more inclusive environments where students with hearing loss are not only present, but actively and meaningfully engaged.

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author. The data are not publicly available due to privacy or ethical restrictions.

Funding statement

This work was funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) under Germany's Excellence Strategy – EXC 2177 /1 – Project ID 390,895,286, as well as by the Niedersächsisches Ministerium für Wissenschaft und Kultur (MWK, Ministry of Science and Culture) within the funding scheme 'ExzellenzStärken'.

Ethics approval statement

Ethics approval for data collection was granted by the central ethics committee of the Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Lara Hardebeck: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Esther Ruigendijk:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Conceptualization. **Ulla Licandro:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Acknowledgments

We would like to thank all students and their parents who participated in this study as well as their teachers and schools for supporting our research. Additionally, we would like to thank Paula Bartsch for helping us with data preparation.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.ijer.2025.102874](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2025.102874).

References

- Adams, W. C. (2015). Conducting semi-structured interviews. In K. E. Newcomer, H. P. Hatry, & J. S. Wholey (Eds.), *Handbook of practical program evaluation* (1st ed., pp. 492–505). Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119171386.ch19>.
- Borders, C. M., Barnett, D., & Bauer, A. M. (2010). How are they really doing? Observation of inclusive classroom participation for children with mild-to-moderate deafness. *Journal of Deaf Studies and Deaf Education*, 15(4), 348–357. <https://doi.org/10.1093/deafed/enq028>
- Bossaert, G., Colpin, H., Pijl, S. J., & Petry, K. (2013). Truly included? A literature study focusing on the social dimension of inclusion in education. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 17(1), 60–79. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2011.580464>
- Brännström, J. K., Von Lochow, H., Lyberg-Åhländer, V., & Sahlén, B. (2019). The influence of voice quality and multi-talker babble noise on sentence processing and recall performance in school children using cochlear implant and/or hearing aids. *Logopedics Phoniatrics Vocology*, 44(2), 87–94. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14015439.2018.1504984>
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp0630a>
- Carlberg, L., & Granlund, M. (2019). Achievement and participation in schools for young adolescents with self-reported neuropsychiatric disabilities: A cross-sectional study from the southern part of Sweden. *Scandinavian Journal of Public Health*, 47(2), 199–206. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1403494818788415>
- Cerney, J. (2007). *Deaf education in america: Voices of children from inclusion settings*. Gallaudet University Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctv2rr3dddq>
- Crandell, C. C., & Smaldino, J. J. (2000). Classroom acoustics for children with normal hearing and with hearing impairment. *Language, Speech, and Hearing Services in Schools*, 31(4), 362–370. <https://doi.org/10.1044/0161-1461.3104.362>
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2023). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (6th ed.). SAGE <https://uk.sagepub.com/en-gb/eur/research-design/book270550>.
- Dockrell, J. E., & Shield, B. M. (2006). Acoustical barriers in classrooms: The impact of noise on performance in the classroom. *British Educational Research Journal*, 32(3), 509–525. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01411920600635494>
- Edmondson, S., & Howe, J. (2019). Exploring the social inclusion of deaf young people in mainstream schools, using their lived experience. *Educational Psychology in Practice*, 35(2), 216–228. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02667363.2018.1557113>
- Eriks-Brophy, A., Durieux-Smith, A., Olds, J., Fitzpatrick, E., Duquette, C., & Whittingham, J. (2006). Facilitators and barriers to the inclusion of orally educated children and youth with hearing loss in schools: Promoting partnerships to support inclusion. *Volta Review*, 106(1), 53–88.
- Hatamizadeh, N., Ghasemi, M., Saeedi, A., & Kazemnejad, A. (2008). Perceived competence and school adjustment of hearing impaired children in mainstream primary school settings. *Child: Care, Health and Development*, 34(6), 789–794. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2214.2008.00871.x>
- Hornsby, B. W. Y., Davis, H., & Bess, F. H. (2021). The impact and management of listening-related fatigue in children with hearing loss. *Otolaryngologic Clinics of North America*, 54(6), 1231–1239. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.otc.2021.07.001>
- Imms, C., Adair, B., Keen, D., Ullenhag, A., Rosenbaum, P., & Granlund, M. (2016). ‘Participation’: A systematic review of language, definitions, and constructs used in intervention research with children with disabilities. *Developmental Medicine & Child Neurology*, 58(1), 29–38. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dmcn.12932>
- Imms, C., Granlund, M., Wilson, P. H., Steenberg, B., Rosenbaum, P. L., & Gordon, A. M. (2017). Participation, both a means and an end: A conceptual analysis of processes and outcomes in childhood disability. *Developmental Medicine & Child Neurology*, 59(1), 16–25. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dmcn.13237>
- Israelite, N. (2002). Hard-of-hearing adolescents and identity construction: Influences of school experiences, peers, and teachers. *Journal of Deaf Studies and Deaf Education*, 7(2), 134–148. <https://doi.org/10.1093/deafed/7.2.134>
- Jarvis, J. (2003). ‘It’s more peaceful without any support’: What do deaf pupils think about the support they receive in mainstream schools? *Support for Learning*, 18(4), 162–169. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.0268-2141.2003.00302.x>
- Keerthan, K., . S., Gunjawate, D. R., Ravi, R., & Kumar, K. (2025). Exploring teachers’ knowledge and attitudes towards the inclusion of children with hearing impairment in mainstream education- A systematic review. *International Journal of Pediatric Otorhinolaryngology*, 190, Article 112255. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijporl.2025.112255>
- Klatte, M., Bergström, K., & Lachmann, T. (2013). Does noise affect learning? A short review on noise effects on cognitive performance in children. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 4. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2013.00578>
- Koster, M., Nakken, H., Pijl, S. J., & Van Houten, E. (2009). Being part of the peer group: A literature study focusing on the social dimension of inclusion in education. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 13(2), 117–140. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603110701284680>

- Krijger, S., Coene, M., Govaerts, P. J., & Dhooge, I. (2020). Listening difficulties of children with cochlear implants in mainstream secondary education. *Ear & Hearing*, 41(5), 1172–1186. <https://doi.org/10.1097/AUD.0000000000000835>
- Kultusministerkonferenz [Conference of Ministers of Education]. (2024). *Sonderpädagogische Förderung in Schulen 2013 bis 2022* [Special needs education in schools 2013 to 2022]. In *Sekretariat der Ständigen Konferenz der Kultusminister der Länder in der Bundesrepublik Deutschland* [Secretariat of the Standing Conference of the Ministers of Education and Cultural Affairs]. <https://www.kmk.org/dokumentation-statistik/statistik/schulstatistik/sonderpaedagogische-foerderung-an-schulen.html>.
- Luckner, J. L., & Movahedazarhouli, S. (2019). Social–Emotional interventions with children and youth who are deaf or hard of hearing: A research synthesis. *The Journal of Deaf Studies and Deaf Education*, 24(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1093/deafed/eny030>
- Maciver, D., Rutherford, M., Arakelyan, S., Kramer, J. M., Richmond, J., Todorova, L., Romero-Ayuso, D., Nakamura-Thomas, H., Ten Velden, M., Finlayson, I., O'Hare, A., & Forsyth, K. (2019). Participation of children with disabilities in school: A realist systematic review of psychosocial and environmental factors. *PLOS ONE*, 14(1), Article e0210511. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0210511>
- Malterud, K., Siersma, V. D., & Guassora, A. D. (2016). Sample size in qualitative interview studies: Guided by information power. *Qualitative Health Research*, 26(13), 1753–1760. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732315617444>
- Mattys, S. L., Davis, M. H., Bradlow, A. R., & Scott, S. K. (2012). Speech recognition in adverse conditions: A review. *Language and Cognitive Processes*, 27(7–8), 953–978. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01690965.2012.705006>
- Maxwell, G. R., Granlund, M., & Augustine, L. (2018). Inclusion through participation: Understanding participation in the International Classification of functioning, disability, and Health as a methodological research tool for investigating Inclusion. *Frontiers in Education*, 3, 41. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2018.00041>
- Mealings, K. (2022). A review of the effect of classroom sound-field amplification on children in primary school. *American Journal of Audiology*, 31(2), 470–486. https://doi.org/10.1044/2022_AJA-21-00240
- Powers, S. (2002). From concepts to practice in deaf education: A United Kingdom perspective on inclusion. *Journal of Deaf Studies and Deaf Education*, 7(3), 230–243. <https://doi.org/10.1093/deafed/7.3.230>
- Preisler, G., Tvingstedt, A.-L., & Ahlström, M. (2005). Interviews with deaf children about their experiences using cochlear implants. *American Annals of the Deaf*, 150(3), 260–267.
- Punch, R., & Hyde, M. (2005). The social participation and career decision-making of hard-of-hearing adolescents in regular classes. *Deafness & Education International*, 7(3), 122–138. <https://doi.org/10.1179/146431505790560365>
- Punch, R., & Hyde, M. (2011). Social participation of children and adolescents with cochlear implants: A qualitative analysis of parent, teacher, and child interviews. *Journal of Deaf Studies and Deaf Education*, 16(4), 474–493. <https://doi.org/10.1093/deafed/enr001>
- Sato, H., & Bradley, J. S. (2008). Evaluation of acoustical conditions for speech communication in working elementary school classrooms. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 123(4), 2064–2077. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.2839283>
- Schwab, S., Wimberger, T., & Mamas, C. (2019). Fostering social participation in inclusive classrooms of students who are deaf. *International Journal of Disability, Development and Education*, 66(3), 325–342. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1034912X.2018.1562158>
- Takala, M., & Sume, H. (2018). Hearing-impaired pupils in mainstream education in Finland: Teachers' experiences of inclusion and support. *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 33(1), 134–147. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08856257.2017.1306965>
- Todorov, M., Galvin, K., Klieve, S., & Rickards, F. (2021). Engagement of children who are deaf or hard-of-hearing attending mainstream schools. *The Journal of Deaf Studies and Deaf Education*, 26(3), 395–404. <https://doi.org/10.1093/deafed/enab003>
- Todorov, M., Galvin, K., Punch, R., Klieve, S., & Rickards, F. (2022). Barriers and facilitators to engaging in mainstream primary school classrooms: Voices of students who are deaf or hard-of-hearing. *Deafness & Education International*, 24(1), 2–23. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14643154.2021.1992829>
- Tomblin, J. B., Harrison, M., Ambrose, S. E., Walker, E. A., Oleson, J. J., & Moeller, M. P. (2015). Language outcomes in young children with mild to severe hearing loss. *Ear & Hearing*, 36(Supplement 1), 76S–91S. <https://doi.org/10.1097/AUD.0000000000000219>
- Tsach, N., & Most, T. (2016). The inclusion of deaf and hard-of-hearing students in mainstream classroom: Classroom participation and its relationship to communication, academic, and social performance. In M. Marschark, V. Lampropoulou, & E. K. Skordilis (Eds.), *Diversity in deaf education* (pp. 355–380). Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780190493073.001.0001>.
- United Nations (2006). Convention on the rights of persons with disabilities. United Nations.
- Van Den Heuij, K. M. L., Neijenhuis, K., & Coene, M. (2022). Perspectives of D/HH-students on mainstream higher education: A qualitative study. *The Journal of Deaf Studies and Deaf Education*, 27(4), 385–398. <https://doi.org/10.1093/deafed/enac020>
- VERBI Software. (2024). *MAXQDA 24* [Computer software]. VERBI Software.
- Wie, O. B., Torkildsen, J. V. K., Schaubert, S., Busch, T., & Litovsky, R. (2020). Long-term language development in children with early simultaneous bilateral cochlear implants. *Ear & Hearing*, 41(5), 1294–1305. <https://doi.org/10.1097/AUD.0000000000000851>
- World Health Organization. (2001). *International classification of functioning disability and health (ICF)*. World Health Organization.